

No alarms and no surprises: dynamics of renewable energy curtailment in California

Javier López Prol^{*1}, David Zilberman²

¹Yonsei University Mirae, Dpt. of Economics and Dpt. of Environmental Finance

²University of California Berkeley, Dpt. of Agricultural and Resource Economics

*Corresponding author: jlprol@yonsei.ac.kr

Abstract

As variable renewable energy (VRE) sources like wind and solar increase their penetration in electricity markets, their production has to be curtailed more often due to overproduction, system inflexibility or grid congestion. Curtailment entails a higher levelized cost per unit of usable electricity and could therefore hamper the further diffusion of VRE. We study the effects of variable (wind and solar) and inflexible (nuclear) penetration and demand on hourly VRE curtailment in California (CAISO) between May 2014 and July 2022. All the methods used (OLS, FGLS Prais-Winsten, Beta regression and Generalized Additive Models) show that increasing variable and inflexible penetration increases wind and solar curtailment rates. On the opposite, increasing electricity demand reduces curtailment rates up to around 60% of peak load, where it stabilizes. Solar curtailment is generally higher and more predictable than wind curtailment at the same penetration levels. Despite increasing wind and solar penetration, the effect of curtailment on levelized costs is moderate.

Keywords

Variable renewable energy sources, cannibalization, excess electricity, energy transition, curtailment

Highlights

- Increasing variable and inflexible penetration increases VRE curtailment.
- VRE curtailment increases exponentially as demand declines below 60% peak load.
- Wind and nuclear penetration have similar effects on solar curtailment.
- VRE levelized costs are expected to remain low despite curtailment.
- Battery storage is not likely to be profitable for curtailment only.

JEL codes

C22, D4, Q42

1 Introduction

As solar and wind become the lowest-cost electricity generation technologies in larger areas of the world (IRENA 2020), with costs expected to decline further in the coming decades (Vartiainen et al. 2020; IRENA 2019a, 2019b), their penetration in electricity systems has been consistently increasing. The economics of wind (Van Kooten 2016) and solar (Baker et al. 2013) are significantly different from conventional dispatchable technologies, both in terms of costs (Hirth, Ueckerdt, and Edenhofer 2015) and value (Lamont 2008). Solar and wind only produce when the resource is available and the electricity system has to continuously balance demand and supply. For these reasons, renewable generation may have to be curtailed (i.e. reduce generation with respect to what could be produced given available resources (Bird et al. 2016)) when production exceeds demand, the system is not flexible enough to adapt to intermittency, or the concentration of VRE capacity in a small area causes grid congestion.

There is a rich strand of literature analyzing curtailment ex-ante with different types of electricity system models. Frew et al. (2019) simulates the USA electricity system with high solar penetration and concludes that curtailment does not preclude the economic deployment of solar given photovoltaic cost reductions. Other ex-ante modeling exercises focus on curtailment mitigation options (Villamor, Avagyan, and Chalmers 2020), such as storage (McDonagh et al. 2020), electric vehicles (Dixon et al. 2020) or even load migration across data centers (Zheng, Chien, and Suh 2020).

The analysis of renewable energy curtailment ex-post has mostly focused on China so far, which experienced high shares of wind curtailment due to institutional factors (Xia, Lu, and Song 2020; Qi et al. 2019), market segmentation (Song, De Bi, and Wei 2019) and lack of transmission capacity (Dong et al. 2018). Tang et al. (2018) provide a comprehensive description of the phenomenon and Zhang et al. (2020) compare China's case with other international experiences. Due to its idiosyncratic institutional settings, grid infrastructure and dispatch mechanism, the Chinese case is considerably different from western liberalized wholesale electricity markets.

Golden and Paulos (2015) explain the concept and implications of curtailment, and Bird et al. (2016) and O'Shaughnessy et al. (2020) provide high-level perspectives on renewable energy curtailment trends in the countries with the highest wind and solar penetration. The most comprehensive study (Yasuda et al. 2022) provides a global assesment on the relationship between curtailment and VRE's penetration rates. However, there is no much literature on observed curtailment dynamics with high temporal resolution in liberalized wholesale electricity markets. For this reason, this study presents a detailed analysis of solar and wind curtailment dynamics in California with hourly data provided by the California Independent System Operator (CAISO), including small-scale solar estimates provided by the Energy Information Administration (EIA), between May 2014 and July 2022.

We first estimate the relationship between increasing shares of variable renewables and the share of potential renewable electricity curtailed (curtailment rate), including also the effect of demand and inflexible generation (nuclear). We compare three different linear regression methods: ordinary least squares (OLS), Prais-Winsten feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) and beta regression. Additionally, we estimate and predict wind and solar curtailment depending on each technology’s penetration and demand levels with a Generalized Additive Model (GAM) to better understand potential nonlinearities. Finally, we estimate the effect of curtailment on wind and solar average unit costs (levelized cost of electricity or LCOE). We provide both a wide range of results and potential scenarios for 2030 according to California’s goal to reach 60% renewable energy by then. The results show that increasing both VRE and inflexible generation increases VRE curtailment rates, and that VRE curtailment rates increase exponentially as demand declines below 60% peak load (no surprises). Even at high curtailment rates, VRE levelized costs are likely to remain low, given their expected cost evolution (no alarms). Understanding renewable energy curtailment is important to advance electricity system decarbonization cost-effectively. Knowing its causes may help design mitigation measures and predict future costs and benefits of variable renewables as their penetration increases.

2 Data

2.1 Generation and curtailment

We use hourly generation and curtailment data provided by the California Independent System Operator (CAISO)¹. The variables of interest are wind, solar and nuclear generation and demand (load). Wind and solar are the two main variable renewable energy (VRE) sources, and nuclear is interesting to assess the impact of inflexible generation on curtailment. Whereas nuclear energy has some degree of flexibility and new nuclear technologies offer promising options in that direction, its current operation is mostly baseload. The operation of existing capacity is unlikely to change due to both technical and economic constraints (see Figure 1 in the Appendix for a comparison between nuclear and non-nuclear thermal (i.e. gas and coal) hourly generation profiles in California in 2021).

The CAISO data includes only generation from centralized utility-scale installations. Omitting small-scale solar generation would overestimate curtailment rates, as the actual penetration of solar is higher than the numbers derived from large-scale installations alone (see López Prol et al. (2020) for an illustration of this potential overestimation for the cannibalization effect). For this reason, We take small-scale monthly photovoltaic (PV) generation from the Energy Information Administration (form EIA-861M²)

¹Data publicly available at <http://www.caiso.com/informed/Pages/ManagingOversupply.aspx>.

²Data publicly available at <https://www.eia.gov/electricity/data/eia861m/>.

and interpolate to hourly assuming the same generation pattern as the centralized generation provided by the EIA. Then we sum both centralized and small-scale solar generation to obtain total solar generation, and also small-scale solar generation and demand to obtain total demand, including thus electricity self-consumption. This is equivalent to assuming that no small-scale PV electricity is curtailed. This is a reasonable assumption, as most PV self-consumption in California has been so far installed under a net-metering system, in which surplus electricity exported to the grid is remunerated at the same price as retail electricity, so prosumers have no incentive to curtail generation (see López Prol and Steininger (2017) for details on different photovoltaic self-consumption regulation schemes).

Figure 1. (a) Monthly solar and wind curtailment rate (% of potential generation) and (b) penetration (% of demand) in California between May 2014 and July 2022.

We express all variables in percentage terms to obtain more generalizable results interesting for a broad audience beyond California. We use hourly solar, wind and nuclear penetration as a share of total demand, and demand itself is defined as a percentage of the maximum demand recorded in the period studied (i.e. as a share of peak load). Finally, we calculate the percentage of curtailed electricity for solar and wind as the share of curtailment divided by total potential generation (i.e. actual generation plus curtailment).

Figure 1 shows the monthly evolution of the solar and wind curtailment rates (a), and penetration as a percentage of demand (b). Solar curtailment rate increased in the last years (except 2021) and shows a seasonal pattern with high curtailment rates in spring due to high solar generation and low demand, and low in summer due to peak demand despite still high solar generation. On the other hand, wind presents a declining trend with curtailment spikes clustered around a few months mainly during the first years of the time series. Both solar and wind penetration show the same seasonal pattern, higher in spring and lower in winter. Solar curtailment rate increased faster than penetration. Wind penetration increased

slower than solar whereas wind curtailment rate declined. Figures for nuclear penetration and demand, as well as detailed summary statistics for all variables are provided in the Appendix.

The curtailment rates daily profiles resemble wind and solar generation patterns (Figure 2a). Wind curtailment and generation are more randomly distributed along the day, whereas solar generation and curtailment rate are concentrated in the central hours of the day. Figure 2b shows the 2021 curtailment rate duration curve, i.e. the hours of the year (cropped at the hour 2000 for clarity) sorted in descending order of curtailment rate. Solar has a few hours with high curtailment rates reaching 100% in some cases and falling rapidly towards zero. Wind curtailment shares are generally lower and fall even sharper than solar, so in most hours of the year wind curtailment is close to zero.

Figure 2. Stylized facts of solar and wind curtailment rates. (a) Average daily pattern and (b) curtailment rate duration curves in 2021.

2.2 Battery storage

Electricity storage will have a major role on the integration of variable renewables (López Prol and Schill 2021; Haas et al. 2022). Although batteries could be used to store excess electricity, reducing thus renewable energy curtailment, marginal storage costs are still higher than the value of the excess electricity (see section 5.2). Even when profitable, Schill (2020) shows that some curtailment is economic even in the presence of battery storage and sector coupling. Battery storage capacity trippled in both energy and power terms between 2014 and 2020 and skyrocketed (x6) in 2021 (Figure 3a). Storage deployment is expected to keep rising given its continuous cost decline and increasing value it provides to the system as variable renewables penetration increase (Mallapragada, Sepulveda, and Jenkins 2020). Battery storage has multiple applications, from providing 24/7 electricity to isolated systems to enhancing grid resiliency. Figure 3b shows the battery capacity used for each application in California in 2021

according to the EIA form 860³. Capacities sum up to more than the total installed capacity shown in Figure 3a because the same capacity may be used for several applications, as they are not mutually exclusive. These data show that most of the available storage capacity is used for ramping and spinning reserve and energy arbitrage. According to Schmalensee (2021), storage capacity in California is currently used mostly for distribution grids and ancillary services rather than for managing VRE volatility. However, the energy capacity used for excess electricity increased by one order of magnitude between 2020 and 2021, so the role of storage to integrating renewables is expected to increase in the future.

Figure 3. (a) Energy and power battery capacity in California between 2016-2021. (b) Energy and power battery capacity available for different applications in California in 2021. Extended labels: *Frequency* Regulation, Ramping/Spinning *Reserve*, Co-Located *Renewable* Firming, Transmission and Distribution Deferral (*Grid*), System *Peak* Shaving, *Voltage* or Reactive Power Support, *Backup* Power, *Excess* Wind and Solar Generation, Load *Follow* and Load *Manage*.

2.3 Wind and solar costs

The installation cost data used to calculate the unit cost of solar and wind depending on the curtailment rate is taken from IRENA future cost reports (IRENA 2019a, 2019b). Given the historical overestimation of renewable energy costs by international organizations (Hoekstra, Steinbuch, and Verbong 2017), we take the lower bound of the cost provided by IRENA, corresponding to the fifth percentile, for the baseline future scenario. We present a wide range of potential values in section 4.3, so this assumption is only for illustrative purposes. We assume a 5% discount rate and 30 years lifetime for both technologies, and an annual generation of 1,800 and 2,400 kWh/kWp for solar and wind, respectively. The value for solar corresponds to the yield of solar photovoltaics in the plains of central California according to the

³Data publicly available at <https://www.eia.gov/electricity/data/eia860/>, accessed on 2022-03-13.

Global Solar Atlas (World Bank 2020). The value for wind is the result of dividing wind generation by installed capacity in California in 2019.

3 Methods

3.1 Linear models

The Phillips-Perron test rejects the null hypothesis of unit root for all the interest variables (Table 8 in the Appendix). Accordingly, we assume that all our time series are stationary. We want to explain hourly wind and solar curtailment rates (share of electricity curtailed over potential generation, $y_t^{\{w,s\}}$) as a function of wind, solar and nuclear penetration, demand (expressed as a share of peak load) and time dummies including hours of the day, days of the week, months of the year and year. We apply a logit transformation with proportions remapped to (0.025, 0.975) to our dependent variables to consider the truncated nature of percentage data.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{logit}(y_t^{\{w,s\}}) = & \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Solar}_t + \beta_2 \text{Wind}_t + \beta_3 \text{Nuclear}_t + \beta_4 \text{Demand}_t + \\ & \gamma_1 \text{Hour}_t + \gamma_2 \text{Day}_t + \gamma_3 \text{Month}_t + \gamma_4 \text{Year}_t + \epsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

We do not explicitly model battery (dis)charge from equation 1 because it is not primarily used for curtailment (Figure 3 and Schmalensee (2021)). Still, the increasing trend in storage capacity as well as any potential seasonality would be captured by the year fixed effects and the remaining time dummies.

To ensure the correctness and robustness of our estimates, we take a threefold approach to modeling the aforementioned relationships:

- Ordinary least squares (OLS): the logit transformation applied to our outcome variable allows us to perform an OLS regression with proportion data. Residuals exhibit both heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation, so we report autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity consistent (HAC) Newey West standard errors.
- Feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) with Prais-Winsten estimator (Prais and Winsten 1954), assuming that the residuals follow a first order autoregressive process AR(1) such that $\epsilon = \rho\epsilon_{t-1} + \omega$, where $|\rho| < 1$ and ω is a white noise. This method explicitly models the autorregressive process, eliminating residual autocorrelation and providing more efficient estimates.
- Beta regression (Ferrari and Cribari-Neto 2004; Cribari-Neto and Zeileis 2010) is more flexible than the previous as it assumes that the dependent variable is beta-distributed and includes a logit link to account for the proportion nature of the outcome variable, which is additionally transformed

as $(y \cdot (n - 1) + 0.6)/n$, where n is the sample size to avoid the extreme values (0, 1) following Smithson and Verkuilen (2006)⁴. The specification of the beta regression is thus

$$g(\mu_t) = \tilde{\alpha} + \tilde{\beta}_1 Solar_t + \tilde{\beta}_2 Wind_t + \tilde{\beta}_3 Nuclear_t + \tilde{\beta}_4 Demand_t + \tilde{\gamma}_1 Hour_t + \tilde{\gamma}_2 Day_t + \tilde{\gamma}_3 Month_t + \tilde{\gamma}_4 Year_t \quad (2)$$

3.2 Generalized additive model (GAM)

The high concentration of curtailment rates in a few hours of the year (Figure 2b) suggests that the data generation process may be nonlinear. To identify with more detail potential nonlinearities we explore the relationship between our interest variables with a generalized additive model (GAM). Now each variable is modelled as a smooth made up by k basis functions. GAMs balance likelihood and wiggliness to capture nonlinear relationships without overfitting the noise through (i) a smoothing parameter λ that is automatically selected by the restricted maximum likelihood (REML) method, and (ii) the number of basis functions k that make up the smooth (Wood 2017). We again assume a beta distribution and apply a logit link.

The relationships of interest are the same as before, but the model specification differs. Now we explain solar and wind curtailment rates as function of solar, wind, nuclear and demand smooths (combinations of k basis functions). Additionally, we include a time (sequence of numbers at hourly level) smooth to capture autocorrelation, hour of the day and day of the week smooths to capture diurnal and weekly patterns, a month of the year smooth to capture seasonality and year fixed effect to capture any year-specific shock, such as the pandemic-induced demand contraction in 2020 (López Prol and O 2020). We use penalized regression splines as basis functions for the main effects, and cyclic cubic splines with 24, 7 and 12 basis functions (k) for the hour, day and month variables, respectively, to correctly specify their seasonal nature.

$$g(\mu_t) = \tilde{\alpha} + f(Solar_t) + f(Wind_t) + f(Nuclear_t) + f(Demand_t) + f(time_t) + f(Hour_t) + f(Day_t) + f(Month_t) + \tilde{\gamma} Year_t \quad (3)$$

Once we estimated the GAM, we predict the partial effects of each of the interest variables *ceteris paribus*, using average 2021 values as a baseline for the other variables. This allows us to see the nonlinear effect of each independent variable on the solar and wind curtailment rates while holding all the other variables constant at their most recent mean 2021 levels.

⁴The original transformation proposed by Smithson and Verkuilen (2006) is $(y \cdot (n - 1) + 0.5)/n$. We choose a parameter of 0.7 instead of 0.5 to make all models defined with the same transformation. Trying a range of different parameters between 0.2-0.8 in individual models with different samples confirms the robustness of the estimates across the parameter range.

4 Results

4.1 Linear partial effects

Figure 4 summarizes the regression results presented in Table 1. All variables are expressed in proportions and due to the logit transformation of the dependent variable the coefficients have to be interpreted in terms of log-odds. Next section provides more detailed, backtransformed partial effects. The conclusions of the linear models are the following:

- Variable penetration increases solar and wind curtailment rates. The three methods agree that solar penetration increases wind and solar curtailment, and that wind penetration increases solar curtailment. Although the OLS and Prais-Winsten methods fail to identify a significant effect of wind penetration on its own curtailment rate, the most reliable of these three, the Beta regression, and the more flexible GAM in the next section confirm that wind penetration also increases curtailment rates, particularly at high penetration and low demand.

Figure 4. Partial effects of solar, wind and nuclear penetration (% of demand) and demand (% of peak load) on solar and wind curtailment rate (% of potential generation). 99% confidence intervals with heteroskedasticity or heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent standard errors when necessary. See Table 1 for details.

- Inflexible penetration (nuclear) shows positive coefficients for both solar and wind curtailment, but only statistically significant at 99% confidence for solar. The nonlinear estimation in the next section will confirm that effect is also positive for the case of wind curtailment.
- Higher demand is associated with lower levels of wind and solar curtailment rates.

The results across estimation methods are robust, particularly for solar penetration and demand. There is higher uncertainty for nuclear and wind penetration that we will discuss further in the next section. The OLS and the FGLS coefficients are directly comparable (equation 1), but those should only be compared with the coefficients of the beta regression (equation 2) in terms of sign and significance, but not scale. There is some degree of multicollinearity because we express all variables as a share of demand (or peak load in the case of demand itself) which likely causes higher uncertainty and wider confidence intervals (see variance inflation factors in the Appendix). This does not pose a fundamental problem thanks to the high data resolution and variation that allows for confident inference despite collinearity.

	Curtailment rate					
	Solar (OLS)	Wind (OLS)	Solar (FGLS)	Wind (FGLS)	Solar (Beta)	Wind (Beta)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Solar	0.006*** (0.001)	0.005*** (0.001)	0.005*** (0.0004)	0.003*** (0.0004)	0.023*** (0.001)	0.009*** (0.001)
Wind	0.015*** (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)	0.016*** (0.001)	-0.002** (0.001)	0.011*** (0.001)	0.016*** (0.001)
Nuclear	0.013*** (0.003)	0.002 (0.003)	0.013*** (0.002)	0.002 (0.002)	0.011*** (0.002)	0.002 (0.003)
Demand	-0.017*** (0.001)	-0.006*** (0.001)	-0.017*** (0.001)	-0.007*** (0.001)	-0.009*** (0.001)	-0.009*** (0.001)
Time dummies	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>
Standard Errors	<i>HAC</i>	<i>HAC</i>	<i>HC</i>	<i>HC</i>	<i>HAC</i>	<i>HAC</i>
Rho			0.3514	0.6297		
Durbin-Watson (stat.)	1.305	0.743	2.072	2.193	1.586	0.71
Durbin-Watson (p)	0	0	1	1	0	0
Breusch-Pagan (stat.)	2793.729	2760.238	2966.314	1981.357	2545.211	1748.009
Breusch-Pagan (p)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Observations	72,313	72,313	72,313	72,313	72,313	72,313
R ²	0.214	0.085	0.934	0.936	0.526	0.185
Adjusted R ²	0.213	0.084	0.934	0.936		
Log Likelihood					436,077.000	500,659.300
Residual Std. Error	0.628	0.439	0.589	0.341		
F Statistic	378.073***	129.339***	19,689.010***	20,285.660***		

Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table 1 Results of the OLS and FGLS (equation 1) and Beta (equation 2) regressions for wind and solar curtailment rates dependent variables (proportion of potential generation, logit transformation for OLS and FGLS and logit link and additional $(y \cdot (n - 1) + 0.6)/n$ transformation for beta regression).

4.2 Nonlinear effects

The previous results confirm the expectations that increasing penetration of both variable renewables and inflexible generation increase solar and, with higher degree of uncertainty, wind curtailment rates. On the other hand, higher demand is associated with lower curtailment rates. We turn now to study nonlinearities to have a more detailed picture of the general effects identified above and clarify the high uncertainty of wind curtailment rates.

Equation 3 outlines the GAM that we estimate to identify nonlinear effects. Once estimated, the dependent variables, solar and wind curtailment rates, are predicted depending on each variable’s observed range to visualize their partial effects. To identify partial effects *ceteris paribus*, the other variables are set to their average values in 2021.

	edf	Ref.df	Chi.sq	p-value
Solar	7.923	8.684	1,339.431	0
Wind	3.471	4.355	117.612	0
Nuclear	1.102	1.197	15.585	0
Demand	7.338	8.342	270.074	0
Time	7.104	8.318	35.954	0
Hour	12.617	22	1,245.922	0
Day	4.010	5	75.998	0
Month	7.858	10	77.217	0

R-sq.(adj) = 0.0255; Dev. expl'd = 65.5%; n = 67,226

Table 2 Generalized additive model results (equation 3) for solar curtailment rates with beta family and logit link.

	edf	Ref.df	Chi.sq	p-value
Solar	5.566	6.728	215.352	0
Wind	7.150	8.201	328.080	0
Nuclear	1.018	1.035	0.820	0.373
Demand	7.252	8.280	312.942	0
Time	8.660	8.974	154.157	0
Hour	10.126	22	307.588	0
Day	3.580	5	59.774	0
Month	6.148	10	52.949	0

R-sq.(adj) = 0.0137; Dev. expl'd = 14.9%; n = 67,226

Table 3 Generalized additive model results (equation 3) for wind curtailment rates with beta family and logit link.

Tables 2 and 3 show the results for the smooths of the GAM estimation for solar and wind curtailment rates, respectively. The results confirm that all variables are significant at 99% confidence for both wind and solar curtailment rates, except the effect of nuclear on wind curtailment, which is only significant

at 63% confidence. The estimated degrees of freedom (edf) show how nonlinear the relationships are: a value of 1 indicates a linear relationship and the higher edf the more nonlinear relationship. Focusing on our main interest variables we can see (in Tables 2 and 3 and Figure 5) that solar penetration and demand are the most nonlinear variables, whereas the effect of nuclear is practically linear in both cases. The effect of wind penetration on solar curtailment is similar both in shape and magnitude to that of nuclear.

Figure 4. Non-linear effects of solar, wind and nuclear penetration (% of demand) and demand (% of peak load) on solar and wind curtailment rate (% of potential generation). These effects are estimated by the generalized additive model presented in equation 3 and calibrated according to the average conditions in 2021 with 99% confidence intervals. Note that the y axes have different scales.

The edf in Table 3 suggests that the effect of wind penetration on wind curtailment rate is highly nonlinear. However, Figure 5.b shows that the nonlinearity happens only at very low wind penetration. Looking at the dynamics of wind curtailment and penetration in Figure 1, this may be related to the inability to integrate wind generation in the first years of our time series, which seems to have been resolved in the following years, causing thus a more stable positive trend as wind penetration increases. This nonlinearity at low wind penetration is likely the cause why the linear models struggle to identify the correct relationship. The beta regression is the closest to identifying the overall relationship.

Finally, demand shows the same pattern for both solar and wind curtailment. Curtailment rates are high at low demand levels but decline as demand increases. The effect of demand on curtailment rates stabilizes at around 60% of peak load.

Similar to collinearity for the linear models, concavity is high because all variables are expressed as a share of demand (or peak load for demand itself), which causes larger confidence intervals, but do not bias the estimation (see concavity results in the Appendix).

4.3 Effects of curtailment on renewables unit cost

We provide below a wide range of levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) estimates (\$/MWh) as a function of curtailment rates and installation cost with the simplified LCOE formula:

$$LCOE = \frac{IC \cdot CRF}{8760 \cdot CF \cdot (1 - \mathbf{E}(\hat{y}))} \quad (4)$$

$$CRF = \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1}$$

Where IC is the total investment cost, CRF is the capital recovery factor (i.e. the investment annuity, with i being the interest rate and n the investment duration), CF is the capacity factor and $\mathbf{E}(\hat{y})$ is the expected curtailment rate, that can be estimated with any of the methods outlined above. This formula simplifies the LCOE calculation by summarizing yearly costs (in dollars per unit of capacity for a year) in the numerator and dividing them by yearly production (the capacity factor times the hours of the year), including the cost of the curtailed electricity ($1 - \mathbf{E}(\hat{y}_t)$). This is therefore the average unit cost of the usable electricity, including the cost of the curtailed electricity.

Figure 5 shows the LCOE of wind and solar in California depending on installation cost and curtailment rate. The white lines represent the evolution of the unit cost between 2014 and 2019. A ribbon opens between 2019 and 2030 representing the plausible unit costs according to the results of the GAM model presented above and the 2030 low-end cost estimations according to IRENA future costs reports (IRENA 2019a, 2019b). This ribbon shows the range of LCOE assuming that (i) the relationships between variables remain the same as in the past and (ii) the hourly results are generalizable at yearly scale. Because these assumptions are too strict, the white ribbon is merely illustrative rather than predictive.

Future electricity systems will be different in at least two ways. On the one hand, the electricity system will likely adapt to higher shares of VRE by increasing storage, demand response and other flexibility options, which would reduce curtailment rates. On the other hand, it is likely that stronger nonlinearities occur at higher penetration levels, particularly for solar due to its concentrated generation profile. That could entail that curtailment could increase exponentially from some point. Although this is a possibility worth considering, there is neither evidence in the results presented here, nor in previous ex-ante results simulating electricity systems with high VRE penetration (Frew et al. 2019).

The uncertainty range in the curtailment rate in 2030 shown in Figure 5 is the combination of two elements: (i) the 99% prediction intervals of the GAM model, and (ii) the uncertainty in the composition of the electricity mix. California aims to reach 60% renewable penetration in 2030. To achieve these results, we predict a range of possibilities between 20% and 40% penetration each for wind and solar, and then take the extreme values corresponding to the maximum possible uncertainty.

Figure 5. Solar and wind levelized cost of electricity (\$/MWh) as a function of the curtailment rate (% of potential generation) and installation cost (\$/kWp) according to equation 4. The solid white lines represent the path between 2014-2019, and the evolution to 2030 according to IRENA future cost estimation low end and the curtailment rates predicted by the generalized additive model presented in equation 3 at 60% VRE generation with different combinations of wind and solar between 20-40%.

These results suggest that curtailment is not likely to present a fundamental barrier for VRE penetration given its expected cost reductions. This is consistent with previous findings from ex-ante models (Frew et al. 2019). For instance, at the 2030 expected installation cost and even assuming that half of the electricity is curtailed, LCOE would be around 30€/MWh for solar and around 50 \$/MWh for wind. Even at 2019 installation cost levels and 20% curtailment share, both wind and solar would still cost less than 45 \$/MWh.

5 Discussion

5.1 Robustness

The general agreement of the results provided by the OLS, the Prais-Winsten FGLS and the beta regressions suggest that we have robustly identified the relationships between our interest variables. Additionally, the generalized additive model estimation and the illustration of the partial effects confirm the robustness of our estimates and shed light on their nonlinear relationships. Solar curtailment rates are higher than wind due to its higher generation autocorrelation (i.e. its generation is more concentrated in a few hours around noon, see Figure 2a). Likewise, the solar curtailment models perform generally better: have higher explanatory power and lower uncertainty.

We perform two additional robustness checks. First, we run again the beta regression (the most accurate of the three given its flexibility) for each year with full data (2015-2021) separately to check coefficients' stability across time. Figure 3 in the Appendix shows that all coefficients are consistent across time with the only exception of nuclear penetration in 2019. Finally, we aggregate the data to daily resolution to check whether the results are still valid at higher timescales. Figure 4 in the Appendix shows that all the point estimates have the same sign as the hourly estimations, but the uncertainty increases due to the attenuation bias caused by the time aggregation. These results show that the coefficients are robust across time-scales but highlight the relevance of high-resolution data to study curtailment dynamics.

5.2 Curtailment mitigation and storage profitability

The California Independent System Operator (CAISO) lists eight main potential curtailment mitigation options: (i) storage, (ii) expansion of energy imbalance markets, (iii) demand response, (iv) regional coordination, (v) time-of-use rates, (vi) electric vehicles, (vii) reducing minimum operating levels (i.e. inflexible generation), and (viii) flexible resources⁵. They may be summarized in three broad options: (i) system flexibility to compensate higher shares of variable renewables, (ii) demand response to increase price elasticity, such that consumption adapts to generation patterns, rather than the opposite, and (iii) geographical diversification to offset opposite generation and consumption patterns.

Among these options, storage is particularly relevant for the number of applications that it may serve (Figure 2b) and the past and projected declining cost of Li-ion batteries. For this reason, storage deployment is increasing exponentially (Figure 2a) and is expected to increase even faster in the future. However, the use of batteries is not yet widespread in California for curtailment mitigation due to the still high levelized cost of storage (LCOS) and the relatively higher profitability of other ancillary services.

Figure 7 shows the distribution of CAISO peak daily prices (maximum day-ahead price of each day) between 2018-2021, compared to the range of LCOS for the application of "PV+storage" according to Lazard⁶ in log scale. Peak prices are higher than LCOS (i.e. storage is profitable for curtailment) only a fraction of days, but given the skewed distribution of peak prices, they may be up to one order of magnitude higher than LCOS. Increasing peak prices due to higher flexibility needs and declining storage cost will improve storage profitability for curtailment mitigation. Because curtailment mitigation is a niche application, the use of batteries for this purpose may have to be complemented with other applications (Fig 2) to optimize storage capacity utilization, stack revenue streams and achieve long-term profitability over the storage lifetime.

⁵<https://www.aiso.com/documents/curtailmentfastfacts.pdf>.

⁶v4 2018: <https://www.lazard.com/media/450774/lazards-levelized-cost-of-storage-version-40-vfinal.pdf>, v5 2019: <https://www.lazard.com/media/451087/lazards-levelized-cost-of-storage-version-50-vf.pdf>, v6 2020: <https://www.lazard.com/media/451566/lazards-levelized-cost-of-storage-version-60-vf2.pdf>, v7 2021: <https://www.lazard.com/media/451882/lazards-levelized-cost-of-storage-version-70-vf.pdf>.

Figure 7. Distribution of peak (maximum) day-ahead wholesale electricity prices in CAISO per year and levelized cost of storage range according to Lazard⁷ (grey vertical ranges), log scale.

6 Conclusions

We estimate the effects of variable (wind and solar) and inflexible (nuclear) penetration and demand on wind and solar hourly curtailment rates. The results confirm that increasing variable renewables and inflexible penetration increase wind and solar curtailment rates, whereas demand is negatively correlated with curtailment until 60% of peak demand, from where it stabilizes (no surprises). Whereas wind and (mainly) solar curtailment are expected to increase with penetration, the cost of electricity curtailment is not expected to prevent further solar and wind diffusion given their expected declining capacity costs (no alarms). This analysis can be expanded to other electricity systems to verify whether these relationships hold accross countries. Additionally, further analysis should estimate the mitigation effect of different types of system flexibility, demand response and geographical diversity measures.

⁷v4 2018: <https://www.lazard.com/media/450774/lazards-levelized-cost-of-storage-version-40-vfinal.pdf>, v5 2019: <https://www.lazard.com/media/451087/lazards-levelized-cost-of-storage-version-50-vf.pdf>, v6 2020: <https://www.lazard.com/media/451566/lazards-levelized-cost-of-storage-version-60-vf2.pdf>, v7 2021: <https://www.lazard.com/media/451882/lazards-levelized-cost-of-storage-version-70-vf.pdf>.

Data and code availability

Replication package including code and data is available at Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.7322737](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7322737)

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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Appendix to: No alarms and no surprises:
dynamics of renewable energy curtailment in California

A.1. Summary statistics

Table 1: Summary statistics 2014

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Pctl(25)	Pctl(75)	Max
Solar_curt_sh	5,875	0.4	3.5	0	0	0	100
Wind_curt_sh	5,875	1.8	9.0	0	0	0	100
Solar_sh	5,875	4.9	6.0	0	0	10.8	21
Wind_sh	5,875	5.8	4.4	0.0	1.8	9.1	19.8
Nuclear_sh	5,875	7.6	2.1	2.8	6.1	9.1	12.4
Demand_sh	5,875	55.3	10.7	36.2	46.9	62.0	89.0

Table 2: Summary statistics 2015

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Pctl(25)	Pctl(75)	Max
Solar_curt_sh	8,759	0.7	4.6	0	0	0	100
Wind_curt_sh	8,759	1.6	6.7	0	0	0.2	100
Solar_sh	8,759	6.6	8.2	0	0	14.3	28
Wind_sh	8,759	5.4	4.4	0.0	1.4	8.8	19.8
Nuclear_sh	8,759	8.2	2.1	1.1	7.0	9.6	12.3
Demand_sh	8,759	52.9	9.7	36.7	45.7	57.2	94.2

Table 3: Summary statistics 2016

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Pctl(25)	Pctl(75)	Max
Solar_curt_sh	8,783	1.2	7.4	0	0	0	100
Wind_curt_sh	8,783	1.8	7.3	0	0	0.2	84
Solar_sh	8,783	8.8	10.9	0	0	19.4	35
Wind_sh	8,783	6.1	4.6	0.0	1.8	9.6	20.4
Nuclear_sh	8,783	8.4	1.9	3.3	7.4	9.8	12.4
Demand_sh	8,783	52.5	9.6	36.5	45.4	56.6	91.9

Table 4: Summary statistics 2017

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Pctl(25)	Pctl(75)	Max
Solar_curt_sh	8,759	1.2	7.2	0	0	0.1	100
Wind_curt_sh	8,759	0.3	1.4	0	0	0	45
Solar_sh	8,759	11.0	13.6	0	0	24.0	47
Wind_sh	8,759	6.2	4.6	0.0	2.0	9.7	22.0
Nuclear_sh	8,759	8.0	2.2	2.5	6.3	9.6	12.5
Demand_sh	8,759	52.7	10.3	36.4	45.3	56.6	100.0

Table 5: Summary statistics 2018

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Pctl(25)	Pctl(75)	Max
Solar_curt_sh	8,759	1.4	7.7	0	0	0.2	100
Wind_curt_sh	8,759	0.2	1.0	0	0	0	29
Solar_sh	8,759	12.5	15.4	0	0	27.5	54
Wind_sh	8,759	7.4	5.1	0.001	2.8	11.1	23.6
Nuclear_sh	8,759	8.2	2.0	1.7	6.9	9.7	12.4
Demand_sh	8,759	51.7	9.9	36.4	44.5	55.4	92.8

Table 6: Summary statistics 2019

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Pctl(25)	Pctl(75)	Max
Solar_curt_sh	8,749	2.5	10.0	0	0	0.7	100
Wind_curt_sh	8,749	0.4	2.1	0	0	0	64
Solar_sh	8,749	13.5	16.7	0	0	29.4	60
Wind_sh	8,749	7.3	5.3	0.003	2.5	11.3	25.2
Nuclear_sh	8,749	7.5	2.4	1.7	5.2	9.4	13.0
Demand_sh	8,749	50.3	9.3	35.1	43.7	53.9	89.0

Table 7: Summary statistics 2020

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Pctl(25)	Pctl(75)	Max
Solar_curt_sh	8,783	3.0	9.9	0	0	1.0	100
Wind_curt_sh	8,783	0.9	4.1	0	0	0	100
Solar_sh	8,783	14.5	17.6	0	0	31.8	58
Wind_sh	8,783	7.6	5.4	0.0	3.0	11.5	25.2
Nuclear_sh	8,783	7.6	3.0	0.0	5.4	10.0	14.0
Demand_sh	8,783	50.2	10.1	32.1	42.9	54.2	94.6

Table 8: Summary statistics 2021

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Pctl(25)	Pctl(75)	Max
Solar_curt_sh	8,759	2.4	8.4	0	0	1.1	100
Wind_curt_sh	8,759	0.5	1.8	0	0	0	36
Solar_sh	8,759	16.5	20.1	0	0	35.5	73
Wind_sh	8,759	8.8	5.7	0.02	3.8	13.1	27.4
Nuclear_sh	8,759	7.5	2.1	1.7	5.6	9.2	13.3
Demand_sh	8,759	50.7	9.5	33.0	43.9	54.4	88.4

Table 9: Summary statistics 2022

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Pctl(25)	Pctl(75)	Max
Solar_curt_sh	5,087	4.1	10.5	0	0	2.7	100
Wind_curt_sh	5,087	0.8	2.5	0.0	0.0	0.3	29.3
Solar_sh	5,087	19.9	22.8	0	0	43.0	80
Wind_sh	5,087	9.6	6.0	0.3	4.2	14.6	28.3
Nuclear_sh	5,087	8.4	2.0	3.3	7.1	9.9	13.8
Demand_sh	5,087	49.7	8.9	31.3	43.4	53.3	83.9

A.2. Additional data visualizations

Demeaned hourly generation in 2021 (GWh)

Figure 1. Flexible (thermal) vs. inflexible (nuclear) demeaned hourly generation (GWh) in 2021.

Figure 2. Monthly electricity consumption (TWh) and nuclear penetration (%).

A.3. Unit root tests

Table 10: Phillips-Perron unit root test

Lag	Statistic	P.value	Variable	Type
20	-37888.51	0.01	Wind_curt_sh	No drift no trend
20	-38699.23	0.01	Wind_curt_sh	Drift no trend
20	-38809.11	0.01	Wind_curt_sh	Drift and trend
20	-73731.87	0.01	Solar_curt_sh	No drift no trend
20	-64007.82	0.01	Solar_curt_sh	Drift no trend
20	-60993.64	0.01	Solar_curt_sh	Drift and trend
20	-493.66	0.01	Wind_sh	No drift no trend
20	-1512.02	0.01	Wind_sh	Drift no trend
20	-1588.56	0.01	Wind_sh	Drift and trend
20	-1345.11	0.01	Solar_sh	No drift no trend
20	-1734.32	0.01	Solar_sh	Drift no trend
20	-1709.33	0.01	Solar_sh	Drift and trend
20	-35.88	0.01	Nuclear_sh	No drift no trend
20	-549.47	0.01	Nuclear_sh	Drift no trend
20	-552.11	0.01	Nuclear_sh	Drift and trend
20	-29.76	0.01	Demand_sh	No drift no trend
20	-1084.85	0.01	Demand_sh	Drift no trend
20	-1100.76	0.01	Demand_sh	Drift and trend
20	-468.80	0.01	Solar_logit	No drift no trend
20	-44649.90	0.01	Solar_logit	Drift no trend
20	-41842.06	0.01	Solar_logit	Drift and trend
20	-70.17	0.01	Wind_logit	No drift no trend
20	-36538.98	0.01	Wind_logit	Drift no trend
20	-36571.70	0.01	Wind_logit	Drift and trend

A.4. Colinearity and concurvity

Table 11: Variance Inflation Factor

Independent	GVIF	$\widehat{\text{GVIF}}(1/(2 \cdot \text{Df}))$	Dependent	Estimation
Solar	5.7810	2.4044	Solar	OLS
Wind	1.6076	1.2679	Solar	OLS
Nuclear	1.5447	1.2428	Solar	OLS
Demand	5.1406	2.2673	Solar	OLS
Solar	5.7810	2.4044	Wind	OLS
Wind	1.6076	1.2679	Wind	OLS
Nuclear	1.5447	1.2428	Wind	OLS
Demand	5.1406	2.2673	Wind	OLS
Solar	4.0663	2.0165	Wind	FGLS
Wind	1.5121	1.2297	Wind	FGLS
Nuclear	1.6756	1.2944	Wind	FGLS
Demand	4.7010	2.1682	Wind	FGLS
Solar	4.7298	2.1748	Solar	FGLS
Wind	1.5635	1.2504	Solar	FGLS
Nuclear	1.5688	1.2525	Solar	FGLS
Demand	4.9994	2.2359	Solar	FGLS

Table 12: Concurvity

Independent	Worst	Observed	Estimate	Dependent
Solar	0.9191	0.8437	0.6413	Solar
Wind	0.4073	0.3748	0.3274	Solar
Nuclear	0.8316	0.4917	0.4875	Solar
Demand	0.9081	0.8976	0.7370	Solar
Solar	0.9191	0.8273	0.6413	Wind
Wind	0.4073	0.3235	0.3274	Wind
Nuclear	0.8316	0.4898	0.4875	Wind
Demand	0.9081	0.8977	0.7370	Wind

A.5. Robustness

Figure 3. Robustness of the linear estimates over time. Beta regression with Newey-West HAC standard errors, 99% confidence intervals.

Figure 4. Equivalent results to Figure 4 with daily-aggregated rather than hourly data.